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Protocols for the Management of Pediatric Traumatic Brain Injury: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Introdução: Introduction: Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) is a brain injury resulting from an external force, which can lead to changes in brain function. Its definition emphasizes that the clinical symptoms of brain damage may not be immediately evident after the trauma and may manifest later. Various external factors, such as direct impacts to the head and acceleration/deceleration of the brain, can result in TBI. In the pediatric context, TBI is especially concerning, with a significant incidence of approximately 280 cases per 10,000 children, being the leading cause of death in children over one year old and one of the most frequent complaints in pediatric emergencies worldwide. The use of the flowchart proposed by PECARN, based on evidence, is a valuable tool to assist in the evaluation and management of children with suspected cranial injury, helping to safely determine the need for neuroimaging, such as computed tomography. **Objective:** To verify in the literature the importance of using the Pediatric Emergency Care Applied Research Network (PECARN) in the care of children with Traumatic Brain Injury. **Methodology:** This is a quantitative and exploratory literature review that employs the PICO strategy to collect data from databases such as PubMed, Scielo, LILACS, and Google Scholar. **Results:** The reviewed studies indicate that there is still low adherence to instruments that guide safe clinical decision-making for the patient. However, other studies have shown positive results in the use of the PECARN flowchart, with a confidence level close to 100%. This means that patients with relevant brain injuries were not discharged without the necessary tests or evaluations for a more accurate diagnosis. Factors such as repeated vomiting, severe trauma mechanism, and trauma to the parietal or occipital region were identified as having a higher statistical correlation with findings on cranial tomography. In the case of mild head trauma, computed tomography (CT) would be indicated for cases with altered mental status, seizures, linear skull fracture, and diastasis greater than 4 mm, depressed skull fracture, or open skull fracture identified or visualized by X-ray. On the other hand, patients with repeated vomiting (>3 episodes), headache, or momentary loss of consciousness could be observed in the emergency room for up to 6 hours and discharged according to clinical evolution. **Conclusion:** This analysis indicates that there is currently an excessive use of imaging tests in children in emergency services. Therefore, it is crucial to train the medical team, use clinical decision-making tools, and develop effective protocols to assess each case individually. This will bring short- and long-term benefits, including reducing the number of tests requested, resulting in cost savings for hospitals, and reducing children's exposure to ionizing radiation, which can increase the risk of developing cancer in the future.

KEYWORDS: Traumatic Brain Injury; Pediatric Emergency; PECARN; Protocol.

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